

SPRING-IN DEFORMATION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED BENDS

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ABSTRACT

The forming of a composite laminated structure against the mold with corners involves geometric distortion in the structure, which is usually called "spring-in" or "reverse spring-back." This paper deals with the effect of mold radius and laminate thickness on the spring-in angle of Gr/Ep laminated bends formed in autoclave. During the formation of a composite laminated bend, the compaction of the bend causes fiber axial compression and fiber axial compression gives rise to the wrinkling of fiber bundles. Experimental results showed that spring-in angle is larger for thin laminated bend than thick ones and smaller for laminated bend with small radius than ones with larger radius with up to a certain level. A model is developed to predict the spring-in angle of composite laminated bends.

INTRODUCTION

Forming of composite laminated structures against a mold with curvature will result in geometric distortion named spring-in or reverse spring-back, which means the final angle of the product is smaller than the mold angle. The usual method of eliminating the geometric distortion in composite structures is making the mold with taking the spring-in angle into account by trial and error or rule of thumbs.

Few systematic researches on spring-in deformation have been done. It is described that the spring-in deformation is mainly due to the thermal residual stress¹. But the geometric distortion of the cured product does not vanish when it is heated to the curing temperature. This fact shows the spring-in deformation is not dominated by thermal behavior. Soll and Gutowski address the buckling and wrinkling of fibers during forming of thermoplastic composite bend and the quality of the resulting part. The relationship among fiber waviness, tension applied to the parts during forming, and the spring-in angle due to local buckling is shown².

This paper deals the spring-in phenomenon of Gr/Ep laminated bends formed against the mold in the autoclave. The spring-in deformation of unidirectional laminated bends is measured for several mold radii and

laminate thicknesses. Modelling analysis was tried for the prediction of spring-in angle of composite laminated bends.

EXPERIMENT

An aluminum prism with corner radius, R_0 , was used as a mold for the curing of composite laminated bends(Fig.1).

To simplify the spring-in behavior, unidirectional laminated bends are formed using the cure cycle shown in Figure 2. Mold radius was chosen $R_0=1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 12$ (mm) and the number of layers of the specimens is 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 16 plies. The micrography of cross section of the bent region of a laminated bend reveals that the fiber volume fraction of bag side is higher than that of mold side because of compactioning(Fig.3). During forming of composite laminated bends, the compactioning will give rise to the fiber axial compression in the bent region, and this compression results in the wrinkling of fiber bundle when the compressive stress is beyond a certain limit. Usually the wavelike wrinkling is observed in the transition part of flat and bent region, especially in the bagside layers in the thickness direction(Fig. 4). This wrinkling pattern lies in the plane of each layer not in the thickness direction of laminate. The spring-in deformation is measured for the laminate thickness, $h=0.25, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0$ mm with the effect of mold radius(Fig.5). The abscissa is mold radius and the ordinate is spring-in angle in degree. Results show that spring-in angle is larger for thin laminated bends than thick ones and smaller for composite laminated bends with small radius than ones with large radius up to a certain level.

MODELLING ANALYSIS

The following assumptions are made for the modelling analysis of spring-in deformation of unidirectional composite laminated bends:

1. As the autoclave temperature goes up, the resin flows out with the compactioning of a laminate. As compactioning occurs, the fibers in the bent region are compressed axially because of the applied bag pressure. In actual situation, the compressed fibers slip viscoelastically along the fiber direction but for the simplicity of the problem, it is assumed that the fibers in the bent region are restrained from slipping to the flat region by the applied bag pressure.

2. The compressed fibers wrinkle or buckle locally when the compressive stress reaches up to a certain level. These compressive stress remains as residual stress when the composite laminated bend cools down to room temperature. The fibers are supported laterally by the adjacent fibers and applied pressure.

3. The local buckling of fiber occurs not in thickness direction but in the plane of each lamina.

4. The bent region of a composite laminate bend is assumed as a curved beam under residual moment determined by the above assumptions.

The distribution of fiber volume fraction in thickness direction of the composite laminated bend is determined under the following assumptions: 1) the fiber volume fraction of the bent region at mold side is the same as that of flat region, 2) fiber volume fraction of the bent region varies linearly with respect to thickness of the laminate, 3) the fiber volume is the same before and after compaction. The distribution of fiber volume fraction is

$$V(t) = \frac{h^* V^*}{h} + \frac{V^* h^* (h^* - h)t}{2h^3/3 + R_o h^2} \quad (1)$$

where V means fiber volume fraction, h is laminate thickness, R_o is radius of mold, t is thickness direction coordinate and superscript '*' means before compaction.

The fiber axial compression in the bent region due to compaction of the lamiate bends is assumed to vary linearly with respect to the thickness coordinate, t . The compressive stress of the fiber at t is

$$\sigma_s(t) = \frac{-E(t) \{ 1 - h^*/h \} t}{\{ R_o + h^*/h \}} \quad (2)$$

where $E(t)$ is longitudinal modulus at t .

The compressive stress in fiber due to compaction grows up to result in the local buckling or wrinkling of the fiber. The fiber will not wrinkling in thickness direction but in the plane of a lamina due to the existence of pressure normal to the mold and pressure bag. The problem of fiber local buckling in the bent region can be simplified as the fiber supported by the lateral pressure of Winkler type under axial loading. The system potential energy can be expressed as follows for a fiber of cross sectional area, A_f , moment of inertia, I_f , modulus, E_f , under Winkler type lateral support, K .

$$\Pi(t) = \frac{E_f I_f}{2} \int_0^{x_0} \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx - \frac{P}{2} \int_0^{x_0} \left(\frac{dy}{dx} \right)^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{x_0} K y^2 dx \quad (3)$$

determined by taking the variation of the above equation and is

$$P_{cr}(t) = \frac{E_f I_f \pi^2 n^2}{l^2(t)} + \frac{K l^2(t)}{\pi^2 n^2} \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of half wave in fiber direction. Finally, the wrinkling residual stress, $\sigma_w(t)$ is

$$\sigma_w(t) = \frac{P_{cr}(t)V(t)}{A_f} \quad (5)$$

The residual stress at a layer will be whichever the smaller of the two stresses expressed in Eq.(2) and Eq.(5). From the Stress distribution in thickness direction, the spring-in angle can be determined using the curved beam theory.

RESULTS

The following material data are used for the calculation of unidirectional laminate properties: Graphite-As fiber, $d=0.005$ mm, $E_f=224$ GPa, $G_f=14$ MPa, $\nu_f=0.2$, Epoxy matrix, $E_m=3.5$ MPa, $G_m=1.25$ MPa, $\nu_m=0.33$. The compaction ratio, C , is defined as the ratio of thickness of after and before compaction. For this case, $C=0.83$. It is impossible to predict the physical quantity of Winkler spring constant, K , that the appropriate value of $K=20$ MPa is used, which fits the experimental trend. The modelling analysis is compared with experimental results in Figure 6. Experimental results show that the spring-in angle becomes large up to the mold radius of $R_0=6$ mm and it gets smaller for thick composite laminates than thin ones. This trend can be explained using the present modelling analysis. The modelling analysis can predict the spring-in angle for moderately small radius of mold. This shows that the assumptions used in this modelling analysis are reasonable and the mechanism involved in the spring-in deformation of composite laminated bends are explainable using the compaction induced behavior. This modelling analysis considered only the variation of stress in thickness direction but by taking the viscoelastic fiber slip in fiber direction into account will give the better result.

REFERENCES

1. C. Ridgard, "Low Temperature Molding Prepreg Systems for the Manufacture of High Temperature Composites Mold Tools and Components," Proceedings of ICCM-VI, Vol. 1, pp. 1.87-1.99, 1987.
2. W. Soll and T. G. Gutowski, "Forming Thermoplastic Composite Parts," SAMPE Journal, Vol. 24, No. 3, May/June 1988.

Fig.1. Mold for composite Laminated bends

Fig.2. Autoclave Cure cycle

Fig.3. Photo Micrograph of cross section

Fig.4. Interply view showing fiber wrinkling by SEM

Fig.5. Experimental Results.

Fig.6. Comparison of Experimental Data and Moldelling Analysis.